

OPPORTUNITIES TO DEVELOP THE SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF THE TEACHINGS OF EASTERN THINKERS

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Abstract: This article discusses the views of Eastern thinkers on issues of education and morals, child education in Islam. Also, knowledge of educational methods and means of inculcating the ideas, views, and ideas of Eastern thinkers in the creative work of the young generation, and their correct use in life is one of the important features of the teacher's pedagogical skills in the process of pedagogical education. It is explained that it is given.

Key words: Spiritual lessons, Literature and stories, Historical data, Religious education, Education,

The main part: The reforms in the socio-economic, political and spiritual spheres implemented in our country require updates in the education system. The state policy on the reform of the education sector has determined the priority directions of the education system development strategy. In particular, the state program on the implementation of the action strategy in the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 and the priority directions of systematic reform in the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, modern in order to raise the process of training highly qualified personnel with knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities to a new level in terms of quality, to modernize higher education, to develop social spheres and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies opportunities were created to conduct research. The conducted studies are based on the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms

implemented in the country "Decision No. 1 PQ-3775, dated August 14, 2018, "Education of young people with spiritual, moral and physical maturity, a qualitatively new step in the system of providing them with education" Resolution No. PQ-3775 on additional measures to improve the quality of education in educational institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country. // National database of legal documents, 06.06.2018, 07/18/3775/1313. Resolution No. 2 PQ3907, on September 23, 2020, "On measures to raise internal awareness" Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" (No. RQ-637, 2020 September 23)³ was a practical program in the fundamental reform of education. This document in the field of education, along with the recognition that the development of education is a priority area in the Republic, paved the way for modernization in all areas of public education. The main goal of educational reforms is to educate and develop the spiritual qualities of a person based on the rich intellectual heritage of the nation and universal values, modern culture, economy, science and technology, and the achievements of technology. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan SH. Mirziyoyev noted: "If the body of society's life is the economy, then its soul and spirit is spirituality. As we decided to build a new Uzbekistan, we rely on two strong pillars. The first is a strong economy based on market principles. The second is a strong spirituality based on the rich heritage of our ancestors and national values.

Based on the teachings of Eastern thinkers, the possibilities of developing the spiritual and moral education of young students are very wide. This educational system is aimed at developing spiritual and moral value, changing human behavior and increasing humanity. The following options are available:

✚ **Spiritual lessons:** There is an opportunity to give spiritual lessons to young students based on the teachings of Eastern thinkers. Through these lessons, students can learn humanity, respect, patience, kindness, justice and other moral values.

✚ **Literature and stories:** Literature and stories of Eastern thinkers are good tools for teaching spiritual values to young students. Humanity, kindness and other moral values are studied through these literatures.

✚ **Historical Information:** Historical information on Eastern thinkers helps teach young readers about its historical and cultural heritage. Humanity, respect and justice can be learned through this historical data.

✚ Religious Education: There is an opportunity to provide religious education based on the teachings of Eastern thinkers. Through this religious education, students can learn humanity, kindness, respect and other spiritual values.

Together, these will be important opportunities for the development of spiritual and moral education for students and will help to form them as humane, fair and respectful people.

Education is the duty of parents and the right of children. The word "Tarbiya" is derived from the Arabic verb "robba" and means to grow, to increase, to follow, to lead and to reform. Muslim scholars defined "education" in several different ways. For example, Imam Bayzavi describes it as follows: "Education is to gradually bring something to perfection." Roghib Asfikhani defines education as follows: "Education is to bring something from one state to another and bring it to the point of completeness. One of the meanings of education is to grow the religious, intellectual and moral powers of a person with harmony and balance. In Islam, raising children is the most responsible and lasting duty of parents. Other duties end by doing some work or spending property. But the responsibility of upbringing will continue. After all, the real gratitude of parents for the blessing of their children comes out by fulfilling the responsibility of upbringing with honor.

The first condition for fundamentally changing the humanistic direction of the educational system and raising it to the level of the requirements of the new era is to approach it as a whole system and work accordingly. Cultivation of high moral qualities in the young generation, formation of national ideology, respect for our rich cultural heritage, historical traditions, universal human values, love for the Motherland, loyalty to the ideas of independence is the decisive factor of all the reforms implemented in our country. The main goal of our policy in the field of spirituality is to ensure people's deep understanding of their identity, the value of independence, the expansion and improvement of national thinking, and the awakening of the spirit of historical freedom and independence.

The famous Uzbek pedagogue Abdulla Avloniy said that "Education for us is a matter of either life or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster."

Conclusion: There is an opportunity to give spiritual lessons to young students. Through these lessons, students can learn humanity, respect, patience, kindness, justice and other moral values. Spiritual lessons teach students to develop human character, increase humanity, and respect themselves and others. These lessons will

help you grow as a good, kind and fair person. Spiritual lessons teach students to learn spiritual values that are important in life, to carry out their activities in the spirit of humanity and to show respect to people. These lessons teach students to respect themselves and others, be patient, and treat them with kindness. Spiritual lessons help young students learn humanity, justice and kindness, and help shape them as humane and just people.

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